

Diamond-coated quartz crystal microbalance sensors: challenges in high yield production and enhanced detection of ethanol and sars-cov-2 proteins

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Abstract

This study presents the technological progress in the deposition of diamond thin films on quartz crystal microbalance (QCM) sensors. The linear antenna microwave plasma chemical vapor deposition technique effectively grows thin diamond films on QCM substrates (Dia-QCM) differently oriented on the substrate holder in the deposition chamber, resulting in single-sided and double-sided coated QCMs. Each of these coated QCMs offers a distinctive advantage for sensing applications. The double-sided coated QCM sensors exhibited the most effective performance in ethanol detection, demonstrating approx. a 3-fold and 12-fold higher response than single-sided diamond-coated and bare gold QCM sensors, respectively. Furthermore, the single-sided Dia-QCM aptasensors demonstrated superior performance compared to bare gold QCM sensors, with a lower detection limit for S-RBD protein ($LOD_{\text{Dia-QCM}} = 0.09 \text{ pg/mL}$ vs. $LOD_{\text{Au-QCM}} = 0.10 \text{ pg/mL}$). In experiments conducted in human plasma, the Dia-QCM aptasensor demonstrated the ability to detect S-RBD protein at concentrations as low as 50 pg/mL, with high percentage recoveries. These results highlight the potential of linear antenna microwave plasma CVD for the mass production of advanced diamond-coated QCM sensors for various applications.

Keywords: diamond; quartz crystal microbalance; microwave plasma CVD; gas sensor; biosensors

1. Introduction

The QCM is an analytical platform comprising an acoustic resonator where frequency changes are induced by mass adsorption on its surface. In an ideal scenario, this relationship exhibits linear dependence, resulting in high sensitivity and widespread application in sensor development for gaseous and liquid media [1]. Although less prevalent than optical and voltammetric biosensors, QCM biosensors are gaining popularity due to assay simplicity (label-free affinity detection), suitability for miniaturization, and the ability to be ready-to-use without special training or education [2]. Consequently, QCM has emerged as a promising tool in biomedicine, food safety, environmental monitoring, and point-of-care testing of biochemical and immunochemical markers [3,4].

QCM represents a robust biosensing platform that enables the detection and quantification of various disease biomarkers at low detection limits relevant for early infection detection or even routine real-time disease progression monitoring [5,6]. To advance the clinical application of QCM-based biosensors, researchers should prioritize improving their applicability and detection performance under clinically relevant conditions.

Therefore, developing improved methods for functionalizing QCM surfaces is highly demanding. Studies have demonstrated that QCM sensor performance, sensitivity, and selectivity can be enhanced by introducing functional layers, either organic or inorganic [7].

For organic layers, the focus is on improving receptor properties and recognition capabilities, such as increasing the stability of antibodies and nucleic acid receptors. The integration of aptamers with semiconducting materials offers significant potential for developing reliable aptasensors [8]. Aptamers, short-specific oligonucleotides, offer unparalleled selectivity, specificity, and stability, making them ideal bioreceptor molecules for protein biomarkers [9].

Among inorganic functional interlayers, diamond thin films are considered highly promising due to their unique combination of intrinsic properties (wide bandgap semiconductor, broad optical transparency, chemical inertness, biocompatibility) [10]. However, standard chemical vapor deposition (CVD) of diamond films on QCM substrates is challenging. In conventional CVD systems, the chemical reactions are driven by hot filaments (2400 °C) or microwave plasma balls (> 3000 °C), both of which are associated with significant thermal radiation to the substrate heated up to 800 °C. This temperature value significantly exceeds the QCM phase transition temperature (570 °C).

An alternative CVD system, low-temperature linear antenna microwave plasma (LAMWP), can grow diamond films at temperatures as low as 250 °C [11]. The LAMWP system also enables diamond growth on 3D substrates, allowing simultaneous coating of both sides of QCM substrates in a single CVD process, thus reducing energy and time consumption.

Although double-sided coated QCM crystals are uncommon for in-liquid measurements due to difficulties in operating standard oscillator circuits under double-sided immersion in water solutions [12], they may prove advantageous for gas sensing applications by increasing the sensing area and potentially improving sensitivity. Our previous work demonstrated the functionality of a diamond-coated QCM as a gas sensor with good repeatability and fast response [13]. The recent study also highlighted the effect of diamond surface termination (oxygen vs. hydrogen) on the adsorption rate and degree of physiologically absorbed biomolecules (fibronectin and bovine serum albumin) [14].

This work extends our previous research on diamond growth dynamics on QCM substrates using the LAMWP CVD system. We compare vertical and horizontal QCM orientations, evaluate diamond film quality on 3D surfaces, and assess single- and double-sided coating efficiency. Furthermore, we present an aptamer-based QCM aptasensor utilizing a diamond film as the interfacing electrode for the direct and label-free detection of the SARS-CoV-2 spike protein.

2. Experimental

2.1. Fabrication of diamond-coated QCM sensors

AT-cut (35° 15') QCM substrates with a resonance frequency of 10 MHz (from Krystaly, Hradec Králové, Czech Republic) were used for the experiments. They have a diameter of 14 mm and feature two keyhole-shaped electrodes with a diameter of 6.5 mm applied on both sides. The metal electrodes comprise a 30 nm Cr adhesion layer and a 100 nm Au top layer. The surface roughness of the QCM substrates ranges from 250 to 500 nm [14].

The diamond growth was performed in a LAMWP CVD system (AK 400, Roth and Rau AG, Chemnitz, Germany) [13]. Before diamond growth, the QCMs were seeded in a deionized water-based diamond powder suspension using low-power ultrasonic agitation. The QCM substrates were oriented horizontally or vertically on the substrate holder loaded in the deposition chamber (Fig. 1). After deposition, the samples were placed in an oxygen plasma to ensure oxygen termination of the diamond. Two types of diamond films were grown: fully closed and porous diamond (PorDia) films. The sample description and process parameters are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 1. Photos of QCM substrates oriented horizontally or vertically on the substrate holder in the deposition chamber (left) and during the diamond CVD process with ignited plasma (right).

Table 1. Summary of the CVD process parameters used to grow diamond thin films on QCM substrates horizontally (planar) or vertically oriented on the substrate holder in the deposition chamber.

Sample name	QCM Alignment	Diamond morphology	Gas mixture CH ₄ /CO ₂ /H ₂ (sccm)	T _S (°C)	t (h)
H-Dia-QCM	horizontal	nanocrystalline	5/20/100	325±5	30
V-Dia-QCM	vertical	nanocrystalline	5/20/100	*375±5	38
H-PorDia-QCM	horizontal	porous	5/20/25	325±5	30

Abbreviations: T_S – substrate temperature, *T_S – average substrate temperature, which varies in the vertical direction, and t – deposition time.

Notes: The applied microwave power (P_{MW}) and the total pressure were 2x1700 W and 15 Pa, respectively. The reference samples, i.e., the horizontally or vertically oriented nanocrystalline and porous diamond films grown on the Si substrates, are called H-Dia-Si (or V-Dia-Si) and H-PorDia-Si, respectively.

The primary characterization of the samples was carried out using scanning electron microscopy (MAIA3, Tescan Ltd., Czechia) and Raman spectroscopy (Renishaw InVia Reflex Raman spectrometer, UK) equipped with He-Cd laser with an excitation wavelength of 442 nm and an air-cooled CCD detector.

2.2. Detection of ethanol vapors

The proof of concept for single-sided (H-Dia-QCM) and double-sided (V-Dia-QCM) diamond-coated QCM sensors were tested in i) gas sensing (specifically for the detection of ethanol vapors) and ii) biosensing applications. For the gas sensing study, the gas in the test chamber was periodically switched (at 3-minute intervals) between ethanol vapor and synthetic air. The ethanol vapor concentration was stepped from 10 to 100 ppm. The response was measured using a Biolin Scientific QSense Explorer analyzer (Biolin, Sweden) (Fig. 2) for three single-sided and three double-sided Dia-QCMs, including a reference bare QCM without the diamond film (sample Au-QCM). The measurements were carried out at room temperature, which is a significant advantage compared to, e.g., metal oxide and metal oxide semiconductor-based sensors working at higher temperatures ($>200^{\circ}\text{C}$) [15,16]. The results were evaluated based on the shift of the first resonance frequency (Δf_R).

In 2002, Kanazawa et al. found that in addition to the absorbed mass, the mechanical properties of the deposited film also affected the frequency response [17]. They proposed an electro-mechanical model to explain how the characteristics of the active sensing film affect the frequency response. This model could be applied to both steady-state and transient conditions.

Figure 2. Photo of the a) measurement setup and b) the open gas chamber with embedded QCM sample.

2.3 Detection of SARS-CoV-2 protein

2.3.1 Measurement setup and pretreatment of the QCM samples

In the case of the biosensing experiments, the surface was thoroughly cleaned with a Piranha solution in a water bath before utilizing the sensing layer on the top side of the nanocrystalline diamond-coated QCM substrates. The QCM was immersed in a hot mixture of basic Piranha, composed of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), ammonium (NH_3), and water in a volume ratio of 1:1:5 at a temperature of 70 °C for 25 minutes, followed by rinsing in distilled water. This procedure was repeated three times. Subsequently, the Dia-QCM substrates were washed three times with distilled water, then with 90 % ethanol, and finally dried in a stream of nitrogen gas. The purified Dia-QCM was then mounted into the custom-made QCM flow cell (Dr. Andreas Ebner, JKU Linz) and was ready for further modification. The flow cell, with a volume of 25 μL , consists of two distinct components: the lower part is used to secure the quartz crystal and to facilitate electrical connection to the crystal's electrodes. In contrast, the upper part includes the inlet and outlet channels and the tube connections (Fig. 3). Considering the background noise, the measurement accuracy was 0.1 Hz. All experiments were performed in flow mode using a GeniePlus syringe pump (Kent Scientific, USA) with a constant flow rate of 50 $\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The resonant frequency, f_R , was measured by the Maxtek RQCM system (Inficon, USA).

Figure 3. Photo of the a) measurement setup and b) disassembled flow cell with V-Dia-QCM. c) Side view photo of the assembled flow cell in the measurement setup.

2.3.2 Preparation of the sensitive aptamer layer and detection of S-RBD protein in buffer solution

Aptamers, specific for the SARS-CoV-2 virus, were immobilized on Dia-QCM substrates based on the high affinity of biotin to neutravidin (Thermo Fisher Scientific), using biotinylated aptamers. This so-called sandwich method was previously validated and developed by Poturnayova et al. [18]. Their study demonstrates the advantages of strong interactions between neutravidin (NA) and biotinylated aptamers. The aptamer sequence (51-bases, 5'-CAGCACCGACCTTGTGCTTTGGGAG-TGCTGGTCCAAGGCGTTAATGGACA-3') was obtained from MicroSynth [19]. The aptamer stock solutions were prepared by dissolving the lyophilized oligonucleotides in TE buffer (1 mM EDTA, 10 mM Tris, pH 8).

The procedure for preparation of the sensitive layer for detection of SARS-CoV-2 protein started with the modification of the bare QCM (Au-Dia) and Dia-QCM surfaces by 125 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ neutravidin (NA) dissolved in deionized water in a flow injection mode. After stabilization of the resonant frequency shift Δf_R (after 30 min), the QCM surface was washed with deionized (DI) water. However, since aptamers were diluted in a PBS solution (10 mM phosphate buffer saline: 10 mM NaH_2PO_4 , 1.8 mM KH_2PO_4 , 137 mM NaCl, and 2.7 mM KCl, pH 7.4) containing 0.55 mM MgCl_2 , the changes in ionic properties may have affected the acoustics parameters. Therefore, in the next step, the surface of the NA layer was washed by PBS. This step was followed by the addition of 0.5 μM biotinylated aptamers. Subsequently, the sensing surface was rinsed with PBS to remove any physically adsorbed aptamers, resulting in the finalization of the sensing layer to study its interaction with SARS-CoV-2 proteins, which were recombinant spike RBD proteins (S-RBD, Sigma-Aldrich) diluted in PBS. The changes in the series resonant frequency, Δf_R , were continuously measured during the whole procedure. The concentration of the S-RBD proteins ranged from 1 to 1000 pg/mL . Each S-RBD protein concentration was deposited on a newly modified QCM sensor. The sensitivity of the Dia-QCM and bare QCM (Au-QCM) aptasensors was compared. In addition, the specificity of the sensitive aptamer layer (1C APT) was evaluated by testing the sensor surface with nucleocapsid proteins (N-protein, Sigma-Aldrich), also found on the surface of the SARS-CoV-2 virus.

2.3.3 Detection of S-RBD protein in human plasma

The last experimental part is related to the study of S-RBD protein detection in real conditions. For this purpose, human plasma (Helena BioSciences, UK) was used, which simplified the procedure and provided a sufficiently close approximation of the real blood sample. Thus, in comparison to the above-described procedure, in this case, after the preparation of the sensing aptamer layer (NA-1C APT), the last step included the addition of S-RBD proteins in diluted human plasma (instead of S-RBD proteins diluted in PBS). However, before this step, the QCM sensor with the aptamer sensing layer was washed with 10 times diluted human plasma, which was previously filtrated by 0.22 μm membrane filters. Approximately 1 h was required to stabilize the acoustic signal (Δf_R). Subsequently, 2 mL of human plasma spiked by S-RBD 50 and 250 pg/mL , respectively, was progressively injected onto the sensing diamond layer (Dia-QCM sensor) and allowed to react for 35 min. After each injection, the crystal was

thoroughly washed in 10 times diluted plasma to eliminate residual molecules. Filtration and dilution of the human plasma before S-RBD addition were performed to minimize the matrix effects of the sample.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Horizontally versus vertically oriented QCM substrates in diamond CVD processes

Figure 4 compares the results for the Dia-QCM substrates horizontally (H-Dia-QCM) or vertically (V-Dia-QCM) oriented on the substrate holder. First, the optical photo of the H-Dia-QCM reveals a homogenous light interference reflection, indicating a uniform film thickness. The estimated film thickness is approx. 350 nm, as determined by optical measurements on the horizontally oriented silicon reference substrate (H-Dia-Si).

In contrast, the V-Dia-QCM exhibits different colors in the reflection, confirming a film thickness gradient. The photo of the vertically oriented silicon reference substrate (V-Dia-Si) is also included for better visualization. For this sample, the diamond film thickness decreased from 312 nm (top) to 164 nm (bottom) due to the gradients in plasma density and temperature in the process chamber during CVD.

The surface, examined by SEM measurements, showed almost identical morphology (Fig. 4a). All samples, horizontally/vertically oriented QCM and Si, show a completely closed layer consisting of tiny crystals less than 50 nm in size, as estimated from top-view SEM measurements. In addition, the diamond film replicates the rough surface of the pristine QCM substrate, i.e., growing at the bottom of *valleys*.

Raman measurements corroborate the SEM results, confirming the similar diamond quality (Fig. 4b). For H-Dia-QCM, the diamond character of the deposited film is confirmed by a sharp peak found at 1325 cm^{-1} [20]. The offset from the monocrystalline diamond (1332 cm^{-1}) should be assigned to the induced stress and nanocrystalline character of the grains. Next, the Raman spectrum also shows broad bands at 1360 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} , known as the D- and G-bands, which are assigned to the non-diamond sp^2 carbon phases. Nearly identical Raman features were found for the V-Dia-QCM sample (dark and light magenta lines). In this case, the intensity of the peaks, especially the diamond peaks, is reduced due to lower film thickness. Unsurprisingly, no Raman response was observed for the bare QCM substrate (green line), i.e., from the pristine as-delivered QCM substrate. Finally, the reference Si substrates coated with the diamond film (black and gray lines) revealed second-order Raman scattering from Si at 970 cm^{-1} [21].

Figure 4. a) SEM images revealing surface morphology and b) corresponding Raman spectra of Dia-QCM and Dia-Si substrates horizontally or vertically oriented on the substrate holder and corresponding optical photos. There is also the Raman spectrum of the bare QCM (Au-QCM) sample before the diamond deposition.

3.2. Porous diamond-coated QCM substrates

Altering the gas mixture ratio in the diamond CVD process results in the growth of a porous diamond film (Fig. 5). As observed, the diamond film homogeneously covers both the QCM and the reference Si substrate (Fig. 5b), consisting of dendrite-like diamond crystals. The Raman spectrum of the porous diamond film grown on the QCM shows a sharp diamond peak at 1326 cm^{-1} and a weak G-band at about 1600 cm^{-1} , attributed to graphitic phases (Fig. 5a, red line). For the reference Si substrate (green line), only a dominant diamond peak at 1329 cm^{-1} and a broad band around 950 cm^{-1} attributed to the second order of the Si peak are observed. The results suggest that the diamond film is of high quality, containing predominantly sp^3 hybridized carbons with minimal non-diamond sp^2 hybridized carbon.

In contrast to porous diamond, films obtained by top-down processing [22,23] or grown on pre-structured porous substrates (so-called templated diamond growth) [24,25], we achieved the porosity by direct bottom-up growth resulting from plasma-chemically driven processes in the unique LAMWP CVD system. The diamond growth in the LAMWP system does not strictly follow the Bachmann ternary diagram and is feasible even at higher oxygen content (higher CO_2 to CH_4/H_2), i.e., outside the conventionally forbidden region [26,27]. Moreover, in the LAMWP system, even a small amount of CO_2 added to the standard CH_4/H_2 gas mixture significantly enhanced the diamond growth [28]. A higher CO_2 content further increases the amount of oxygen-based species (such as CO , CO_2 , O_2 , or alcohol), supporting the role of atomic hydrogen (i.e., etching of sp^2 hybridized carbon) and, in combination with a low-pressure regime, results in the formation of block-stone or porous dendrite-like morphology [27].

Figure 5. a) Raman spectra and b) SEM images depicting surface morphology of porous diamond film grown on Si (H-PorDia-Si) and QCM (H-PorDia-QCM) substrate. The inset in Fig. 5a represents the optical photo of diamond-coated QCM. Note: ‘H-’ in sample names means horizontally loaded samples.

3.3. Gas-sensing properties of diamond-coated QCM substrates

Figure 6 plots the shift of the first resonance frequency (Δf_R) of three single-sided (H-Dia-QCM) and three double-sided (V-Dia-QCM) diamond-coated QCM sensors as a function of time when applying periodic switching of ethanol vapors and synthetic air. For the H-Dia-QCM sensors, the Δf_R reaches the maximum value

undoubtedly at the end of the three-minute period. In the case of V-Dia-QCM sensors, such a claim is valid for low concentrations of ethanol vapors (<30 ppm). The peak-to-peak shift of Δf_R derived from these measurements was used to evaluate the sensing performance of these sensors (Fig. 6).

Figure 6. The time-dependent shift of the first resonant frequency (Δf_R) of diamond-coated QCM sensors horizontally and vertically oriented on the holder, i.e., single-sided and double-sided diamond-coated QCMs, when applying periodic switching of ethanol vapor (E) and synthetic air (Air).

Based on measured data, the mean values and correlated standard errors of Δf_R were also calculated (Fig. 7b or Table 2). It was observed that the H-Dia-QCM had a 2.1-3.4x higher response to ethanol vapors (in the range of 20-100 ppm) than the bare QCM. Furthermore, the V-Dia-QCM had a 4.1-5.6x higher response than the H-Dia-QCM, resulting in a 12-14x higher response than the bare QCM.

Figure 7. a) First resonant frequency shift (Δf_R) of individual QCM sensors and b) mean values of Δf_R with corresponding error bars for each QCM sensor group dependent on ethanol concentration.

Table 2. Mean value and standard error of Δf_R of horizontally (single-sided diamond-coated) and vertically (double-sided diamond-coated) aligned samples compared to bare QCM as a function of ethanol concentration.

Ethanol concentration (ppm)	Au-QCM	Single-sided diamond-coated QCM (H-Dia-QCM)					Double-sided diamond-coated QCM (V-Dia-QCM)				
	$ \Delta f_R $ (Hz)	$ \Delta f_{R1} $ (Hz)	$ \Delta f_{R2} $ (Hz)	$ \Delta f_{R3} $ (Hz)	Mean value (Hz)	Error (Hz)	$ \Delta f_{R1} $ (Hz)	$ \Delta f_{R2} $ (Hz)	$ \Delta f_{R3} $ (Hz)	Mean value (Hz)	Error (Hz)
10	2	12.4	7.0	12.5	10.6	2.4	13.9	60.4	62.6	45.6	21.2
20	5	21.5	11.4	18.3	17.0	3.8	25.8	89.5	95.4	70.2	29.6
30	7	30.5	16.9	23.0	23.5	4.7	40.9	119.4	127.3	95.8	36.6
50	13	56.5	28.0	35.7	40.0	11.0	129.2	194.5	200.1	174.6	30.3
80	25	92.6	50.6	55.0	66.1	17.7	248.6	330.0	359.3	312.6	42.7
100	45	134.1	77.5	78.5	96.7	24.9	491.3	548.9	576.1	538.7	31.6

3.4. Biosensor assembling and S-RBD detection

This section presents the study of S-RBD protein interactions with the surface of aptasensors prepared on Dia-QCM sensors. Regarding this, the whole procedure (preparation of sensing aptamer layer, washing with DI water and PBS, injection of S-RBD proteins) was monitored based on the shift of the first resonant frequency (Δf_R).

As shown in Fig. 8, chemisorption of neutravidin (NA) significantly decreased the resonant frequency, f_R , on average by 351 ± 43 Hz. The formation of a rigid self-assembled layer of NA on the diamond surface is indicated, consistent with observations for other QCM sensors [29]. In this report, authors declare that the steady-state conditions, where f_R values become stable, are achieved 30 min after NA injection. The application of deionized water to the surface resulted in a slight increase in resonant frequency values. This phenomenon can be attributed to the removal of physically adsorbed NA molecules. Next, since aptamers were diluted in a PBS solution containing 0.55 mM $MgCl_2$, the changes in ionic properties may have affected the acoustics parameters. Therefore, the surface of the NA layer was also washed by PBS. As illustrated in Figure 8, this step resulted in changes in f_R values, consistent with the previously discussed impact of altered ionic conditions on the molecular slip between the sensing layer and the surrounding water solution. The addition of 0.5 μM biotinylated 1C DNA aptamers resulted in a decrease of f_R value on average by 55 ± 2 Hz [30]. The high affinity of biotin to NA resulted in the formation of stable aptamer layers. Subsequently, the sensing surface was rinsed with PBS to remove any physically adsorbed aptamers. The sensing layer was then prepared to study its interaction with SARS-CoV-2 proteins (see Fig. 8).

Figure 8. a) The changes of the resonant frequency, Δf_R , after the addition of neutravidin (NA) dissolved in water, biotinylated 1C aptamers (1C APT) dissolved in PBS with $MgCl_2$, and 50 pg/mL S-RBD protein in PBS. The addition of neutravidin, aptamers, proteins, and surface washings by water (H_2O) or buffer (PBS) are highlighted by arrows. b) Zoom in on the highlighted area in Fig. 8a.

The QCM signal changes were recorded during the QCM aptasensor exposure to S-RBD protein concentrations ranging from 1 to 1000 pg/mL. Each S-RBD protein concentration was deposited on a newly modified Dia-QCM sensor. The sensitivity of aptasensors prepared on the Dia-QCM and bare QCM sensors was compared.

Figure 9 depicts the aptasensor response after adding various S-RBD protein concentrations in PBS, presenting relative changes in Δf_R . The Δf_R values were calculated as the difference between the sensor response after S-RBD addition and the baseline value corresponding to the sensing layer without S-RBD. The detection limit (LOD) was calculated as $\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times (\text{SD}/S)$, where SD is the standard deviation of the response of the curve, and S is the slope of the calibration curve, resulting in $\text{LOD}_{\text{Dia-QCM}} = 0.09 \text{ pg/mL}$ and $\text{LOD}_{\text{Au-QCM}} = 0.10 \text{ pg/mL}$.

Another critical element in the design of sensing surfaces is the minimization of non-specific interactions to prevent the generation of false signals [31]. The specificity of the 1C APT was evaluated by testing the sensor surface with N-protein, also found on the surface of the SARS-CoV-2 virus. The addition of N protein for a period exceeding one hour did not result in significant changes, indicating that the proposed aptasensor specifically interacts with the S-RBD protein rather than N-protein.

Figure 9. Decrease of the resonant frequency, f_R , at various S-RBD protein concentrations. The comparison of the sensitivity of diamond and gold QCM surfaces on which S-RBD was determined is indicated in the graph legend.

3.5. Detection of S-RBD protein in human plasma

Following successful testing of the Dia-QCM aptasensor in buffers, the subsequent step was to examine the sensor's performance in human plasma, which had been spiked with the S-RBD protein. Subsequently, a sample of human plasma spiked with S-RBD protein was added to the aptasensor, and the changes in resonance frequency were monitored as a function of the amount of spiked protein. Then, the changes in the f_s values following the reaction of 1C APT with varying S-RBD protein concentrations in buffer and the frequency response of APT 1C to S-RBD in plasma (expressed as a percentage) were used to calculate response recovery. The resonance frequency change observed upon adding 50 and 250 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ S-RBD protein to human plasma was $19 \text{ Hz} \pm 2 \text{ Hz}$ and $25 \text{ Hz} \pm 1.5 \text{ Hz}$, respectively. The observed decline is less pronounced than buffered solutions, likely due to high-molecular substances in human plasma. It is important to note that plasma and other body fluids can significantly impact the results of these analyses. Certain substances can lead to observing values higher than 100 %, which may not indicate the actual outcome. Our findings indicate a relatively high success rate in detecting the S-RBD protein addition to plasma while keeping the absence of non-specific interactions. Nevertheless, these results more accurately reflect the performance of the diamond-coated QCM aptasensor in conditions resembling real-world settings. Results for both added concentrations are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Recovery of Dia-QCM aptasensor in spiked human plasma by various concentrations of S-RBD. Recovery is calculated as $[(\Delta f_R)_{\text{PBS}}/(\Delta f_R)_{\text{plasma}}] \times 100 \%$, where $(\Delta f_R)_{\text{PBS}}$ refers to the changes of the resonant frequency following the addition of S-RBD at a specific concentration in a PBS and $(\Delta f_R)_{\text{plasma}}$ those in a blood plasma, respectively. Results represent mean \pm SD obtained from 3 experiments in each series.

Concentration of S-RBD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Δf_R PBS (Hz)	Δf_R plasma (Hz)	Recovery (%)
50	19.5 ± 1.0	19.0 ± 2.0	97.0 ± 10.0
250	27.8 ± 1.4	25.0 ± 1.5	91.0 ± 5.6

As illustrated in Table 3, a percentage recovery of $97 \pm 10 \%$ for S-RBD was even quantifiable at 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. For 250 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ S-RBD, the response recovery was $91.0 \pm 5.6 \%$. It should be noted that the range of the Anti-SARS-CoV-2 S-RBD protein Human IgM ELISA Kit is 1.56 – 100 ng/mL [32]. The QCM method appears to be a potentially useful tool for detecting S-RBD as a marker in similarly prepared

samples. However, further development, analysis, and optimization are still required to translate laboratory assays into clinical applications.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates the capabilities of diamond-coated QCM (Dia-QCM) sensors, with a particular focus on their application as aptasensors for SARS-CoV-2 S-RBD protein detection.

Using LAMWP for diamond growth on gold QCM substrates proved to be an effective method for producing Dia-QCM sensors with single-sided or double-sided coatings, as well as porous diamond structures. Each of these configurations offers unique advantages for various sensing applications.

The horizontally loaded QCM substrates, i.e., double-sided Dia-QCM, yielded up to a 5.5-fold higher response to ethanol than vertical loading (single-sided Dia-QCM). Moreover, the double-sided Dia-QCM exhibited a 12-14-fold increase in response compared to bare gold QCM sensors.

In complementary studies, the Dia-QCM aptasensor exhibited superior performance compared to traditional gold QCM sensors, with cca. 10% lower limit of detection for S-RBD protein ($LOD_{\text{Dia-QCM}} = 0.09 \text{ pg/mL}$ vs. $LOD_{\text{Au-QCM}} = 0.10 \text{ pg/mL}$, respectively). This enhanced sensitivity can be attributed to the increased surface area and unique properties of the diamond surface. The specificity of the 1C APT aptamer was confirmed through tests with N-protein, showing no significant interaction and thus demonstrating the aptasensor's selectivity for S-RBD protein. This specificity, combined with the enhanced sensitivity of the Dia-QCM, is crucial for accurately detecting and minimizing false signals in real-world biosensing applications.

Furthermore, the Dia-QCM aptasensor demonstrated promising results in human plasma, a more complex medium that better represents real-world conditions. The sensor successfully detected S-RBD protein at concentrations as low as 50 pg/mL, with high percentage recoveries ($97 \pm 10\%$ at 50 pg/mL and $91.0 \pm 5.6\%$ at 250 pg/mL).

These results underscore the potential of Dia-QCM sensors for clinical diagnostics and point-of-care testing.

These results demonstrate the readiness of diamond CVD technology for the fabrication of Dia-QCM sensors, revealing great potential for rapid, accurate, and cost-effective diagnostic and monitoring tools. Such advancements could be crucial in managing future infectious disease outbreaks and improving environmental and industrial sensing capabilities.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

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Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13143981>.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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